

MEDICAL SCIENCES

FEATURES OF CEMENT FIXATION OF REMOVABLE DENTURES ON IMPLANTS

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Abstract

The article describes the features of cement fixation in prosthetics with fixed orthopedic structures on implants. The groups of cements used in prosthetics on implants are described.

Keywords: prosthetics on implants, cement fixation, types of cements, screw fixation.

In prosthetics on implants, two main methods of fixing orthopedic structures are used - cement and screw. One of the most relevant topics for discussion is the advantage of one or another variant of the connection between the prosthetic structure and implants [1]. The effectiveness of screw fixation over a long period of observation in patients with complete edentulism has been described in the literature for a long time. Recently, new protocols for prosthetics on implants have appeared. In particular, this applies to protocols for early functional loading, where there is a need for simple and reliable fixation on cement, which (compared to screw fixation) is much less covered in scientific research and publications today [2]. Screw fixation provides a rigid orthopedic connection designs with implant abutment. Cement-retained bypasses some of the limitations of screw-retained. These include: cosmetic imperfections, low occlusal stability, difficulty in fabricating passively fitting restorations. It is believed that the cement layer absorbs excessive occlusal load and optimizes its distribution to the implant and bone. With this in mind, cementation is often the choice for implant prosthetics. Advantages of cement fixation:

- 1) there is no gap between the abutment and the prosthesis;
- 2) technically simpler and more economical to manufacture;
- 3) aesthetic or functional problems are easier to fix with cementing.

Disadvantages of cementing:

- 1) loss of access to the screw when it is loosened;
- 2) limited access to peri-implant tissues;
- 3) problems with the replacement of the structure due to changes in clinical conditions [3];
- 4) potential risk of irritation of nearby soft tissues with cement residues.

Orthopedic constructions with cement fixation on implants differ little from traditional dentures by manufacturing technique. That is why the manufacture of prostheses for cement fixation on implants can be considered a common routine work that does not require special training from a dental technician. When the implant axes diverge by more than 17° , it is easier to make a restoration on them with cement fixation, because there are no angled abutments for screw fixation with a screw lead divergence of more than 17° in any system [4]. In addition, when cemented, it is easier to achieve a perfect passive fit due to the 25-30 μm space for cement [5]. When prosthetics on implants in the region of lower premolars and molars, screw holes are extremely unaesthetic due to the impossibility of completely masking them. The shearing of veneering ceramics can jeopardize the controlled distribution of dynamic loads in general [6, 7]. Therefore, preference should be given to cemented suprastructures, where ideal occlusal contacts can be created that remain stable for a long time. When choosing the design and method of fixation of the prosthesis, it is necessary to pay attention to the possibility of removing the restoration.

The need to remove the restoration arises when:

- 1) periodic replacement of orthopedic parts;
- 2) loosening or fracture of the screw;
- 3) abutment fracture;
- 4) modification of the prosthesis after the loss of the implant;
- 5) repeated surgical operation.

The possibility of removing the restoration significantly increases the safety of treatment and is most often absolutely necessary for assessing the condition of implants and adjacent tissues, as well as for professional oral care. After all, it is much more convenient

to study the depth of periodontal pockets, complex sanitation and hygienic manipulations in the absence of a prosthesis. On the other hand, the inability to easily remove the restoration using traditional cements for permanent fixation is the main disadvantage of cement fixation. plaque in the gingival sulcus. Cement residues contribute to the adhesion of microorganisms to the implantation surface, causing peri-implantitis with all its signs: edema, pain, deepening of periodontal pockets, bleeding (or exudate) during probing, radiographic signs of bone loss around the implant [8, 9]. That is why temporary cements are so often used to cement restorations on implants to allow for easy removal of the restoration when needed. Many authors consider it expedient to use temporary cements to fix the prosthesis on several implants [10, 13, 14]. According to the international classification, cements are divided into 8 types: zinc phosphate, silicate, silicophosphate, bactericidal, zinc eugenol, polycarboxylate, glass ionomer, polymer. In orthopedic dentistry, cements are divided into:

- according to the period of fixation into temporary and permanent ones [11];
- by chemical composition for zinc-phosphate, polycarboxylate, glass ionomer, polymer modified cements (glass ionomer cements reinforced with polymers), composite [12].

Of the temporary cements for prosthetics on implants, eugenol-free zinc oxide cements are used. Zinc phosphate cements consist of a liquid - an aqueous solution of phosphoric acid and a powder, the main components of which are oxides of zinc, magnesium, aluminum, silicon, and iron. Disadvantages of zinc phosphate cements: low adhesion to hard tissues of the tooth and metal, shrinkage, low moisture resistance.

Polycarboxylate cements appeared in the 70s of the past

century. Thanks to the polycarboxylate groups of polyacrylic acid

form a chemical bond with the hard tissues of the tooth, are more stable

humid environment. Firm "Ultradent" (USA) produces

eugenol-free polycarboxylate cement "UltraTemp" of two types.

The regular type is intended for temporary fixation of crowns and

bridges for a period of 2-4 weeks. Solid type - for long-term fixation of restorations and prostheses on implants

Modern traditional and modified glass ionomer cements are also used to fix prostheses on implants. GICs for fixation have a number of advantages: biocompatibility, good adhesion to metal and tooth tissues, thin fixing film, low solubility, fluoride release and ease of use. Compomers are also glass ionomers supplemented with resins, but the polyacrylic acid groups in them are formed due to the polymerization of cross-links of the acid-functional dimethacrylate monomer. Modified GICs also have higher adhesion and strength, withstand significant occlusal loads, with almost zero solubility in aqueous media.

When prosthetics on implants, they are used when there is poor anatomical retention (low implant head after preparation), as well as for fixing long bridges.

The advantages of composite fixing cements are as follows: high adhesion, strength, resistance to moisture, high aesthetics. For the hardening method, different types of materials of this group are produced: chemical, light, as well as self-adhesive universal composite cements of the double hardening method.

In recent years, new cements based on polymer rubbers have appeared on the market of modern dental materials, which optimally combine strong fixation with easy removal of the prosthesis if necessary and are designed specifically for fixing fixed orthopedic structures on implants. The main components of the material: multifunctional methacrylates, urethane dimethacrylate, polymerization activator. The main requirements that cements of this group must meet are: high retention (long-term fixation), ease of removal of the prosthesis (easily removed if necessary), low solubility, do not affect nearby tissues, have shock-absorbing qualities, have no taste and smell, be comfortable in use, easy to clean (remains are easily removed from the restoration). To facilitate the removal of the structure, if necessary, manufacturers

It is recommended that a thin layer of R-Y Jelly or other water-based lubricant such as Vaseline be applied to the surface of the abutment.

An analysis of the literature data indicates that there is not enough information about this type of material. The purpose of our research is a thorough study of the properties of cements of this group.

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